

immerse

INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

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Final analysis report after carrying out the research

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Summary

This report will present the final results from the Horizon 2020 project IMMERSE (Integration Mapping of Refugee and Migrant Children in Europe) and maps these results onto the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators. The Dashboard contains a total of 30 indicators that measure migrant children's¹ socio-educational integration results and barriers and facilitators of integration. Fourteen of the indicators are extracted from secondary sources and 16 indicators are extracted from primary data collection with children and schools conducted by the IMMERSE project.

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1 Introduction

The purpose of IMMERSE is to examine the socio-educational integration of refugee and migrant children¹ in schools and other educational environments in their host countries across Europe. This report will present the final results from the data collection carried out during the project and map these results onto the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators.² The IMMERSE Dashboard encompasses a comprehensive array of 30 indicators designed to gauge the status of socio-educational integration among migrant children, as well as to identify the attendant barriers and facilitators of this integration. Fourteen of the indicators are extracted from secondary sources, while sixteen indicators are extracted from primary data collection with children and schools conducted by the IMMERSE project team. The co-creation of the Dashboard of Indicators and the data results that we present in this report were produced in the six IMMERSE countries: Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain. Nonetheless, the overarching IMMERSE project and its corresponding Dashboard of Indicators have been designed to maintain applicability across national borders and encompass a pan-European perspective. The data analysis presented here aims to construct a comprehensive portrait of the socio-educational integration of migrant children, encompassing both their specific national contexts and the broader European landscape.

Section 2 provides a brief overview of the Conceptual Framework of IMMERSE and the Dashboard of Indicators and with reference to relevant literature.

Section 3 provides an overview of the methodology, which included large-scale quantitative data collection (carried out between May 2021 and July 2023) and small-scale qualitative data collection (between March 2021 and February 2023).

Section 4 In this section we present the results emerging from both primary quantitative and qualitative data collected for IMMERSE and secondary data following IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators. We provide a cross-country analysis of the results, and the findings are mapped on to the dashboard of the indicators of integration at the macro, meso and micro levels.

Section 4 presents a discussion on the conclusions on migrant children's integration and its barriers and facilitators.

¹ When we refer to "migrant children" we refer to the whole general population of children with migrant backgrounds. When needed, we will refer to more specific sub-groups. "First generation" children refers to children born outside the host country, in contrast to "second generation" children, who are born in the host country from foreign-born parents. These two groups are jointly considered as "migrant-background" children, in contrast to "native" children. "Refugee children" refers to children who are either asylum-seekers in an European country, or who have been provided with some type of international protection. "Unaccompanied (and/or separated) children" refers to children who have arrived in the country without their parents or legal tutors (and/or who have become separated from them).

² The IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators is a new set of indicators on children's integration results and barriers and facilitators that was co-created with children and stakeholders on the first year of the project. For further details see D1.5 *IMMERSE Dashboard* (Serrano et al., 2020a).

2 The IMMENSE Common Conceptual Framework and IMMENSE Dashboard of Indicators

The main objective of the IMMENSE project was to develop a dashboard of indicators on migrant children's socio-educational integration and provide representative data to impact policy making in the European context. IMMENSE adopts an inclusive and intercultural approach of integration, following the normative framework set out by UNESCO (1994, 2006) and the Council of Europe (2008).³ The main objectives of integration under this framework are:

- (1) that migrant (and other) children reach their full potential
- (2) that migrant (and other) children, as well as their families, become fully recognized members in host societies at the formal and informal levels.

IMMENSE has proposed a conceptual framework for measuring the socio-educative inclusion of migrant children which provides a theoretical basis for a dashboard of 30 integration indicators for migrant and refugee children (Fernández García, Serrano, Fabretti et al. 2020). IMMENSE applied a child-centric approach to develop this dashboard following a co-creative and participatory methodologies. The D1.1 *Common Conceptual Framework* (Serrano et al., 2019) identified the main parameters that are key to refugee and migrant children's integration and provided the analytical basis for the Dashboard of Indicators. The Dashboard of Indicators was developed using co-creation methodologies which included the voices of migrant and refugee children, their families and those who work directly with them in schools, NGOs, and policy makers.⁴

The involvement of children and young people in IMMENSE is a collaborative research process in which children and young people are partners and influencers in the research process (Landsdown, 2011). The recognition of children as agentic requires us to understand the conditions under which children thrive and children's experiences and voices must be at the forefront of research and policy (Winstone et al., 2014; Percy-Smith, 2015; Horgan, 2017; Horgan et al, 2021). To ensure children

³ According to the Council of Europe this inclusive and intercultural model of integration is multidimensional and requires a 'a-two dynamic process of mutual accommodation by all immigrants and residents of Member States that implies respect for the basic values of the European Union ' and "it is the responsibility of the host society to ensure that the formal rights of immigrants are in place in such a way that the individual has the possibility of participating in economic, social, cultural and civil life" (Council of Europe, 2008)

⁴ For a full description of the dashboard and its formation process, see D1.5 *IMMENSE Dashboard* (Serrano et al., 2020a) and D1.6 *Report on the Results of Evaluation System of Socio-educational Integration of Migrant Children* (Serrano et al., 2020b).

and young people active involvement, a Children and Young People’s Advisory Group was established at the beginning of IMMERSE which was composed of 18 migrant and refugee children resident in Ireland. This group acted as an expert group, to reflect on the experiences of children in general (Lundy and McEvoy, 2012) and represent their peers in this process. In addition, children across the six IMMERSE countries were involved in the design and validation of the dashboard and the ensuing research instruments.

The resulting IMMERSE’s dashboard of indicators encompasses integration results and barriers and facilitators of integration and is underpinned by an ecological approach. All these factors take place at one or more nested levels following this ecological approach (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2007):

- A. Micro level: the children and their families
- B. Meso level: physical or social proximal development environments (school, neighbourhood and communities containing the children’s systems of relationships)
- C. Macro level: political, economic, and social systems that structure a given society

The final Dashboard of Indicators is a comprehensive set of 30 key indicators of educational integration of migrant and refugee children in schools, as outlined in Table 1. Fourteen of these indicators represent children’s integration results at the micro level, and sixteen of them map key barriers and facilitators at macro and meso levels.

TABLE 1. Overview of the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators

DIMENSION	INDICATOR	DATA SOURCE
INTEGRATION RESULTS		
Access to rights. This dimension reflects if children’s have effective access to key public systems	Children’s access to compulsory education	Eurostat and national census
	Children’s access to health care	EU-SILC
Language and culture dimension. This dimension reflects specific domains of cultural adjustment that are fundamental during integration processes	Children’s perceived competence in host country’s language	Primary data collection
	Children maintaining their cultural identity while adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competencies	Primary data collection
Well-being dimension. This dimension reflects children’s	Children’s happiness	Primary data collection

subjective hedonic experience of their own lives and their psychosocial adjustment during integration processes	Children's sense of belonging in school	Primary data collection
Social connections dimension. This dimension relates to the features of the social networks that children maintain with key figures and institutions.	Children's support from friends and peers	Primary data collection
	Children's intercultural bridges	Primary data collection
	Children's support from teachers	Primary data collection
	Children's trust in institutions	Primary data collection
Educational achievement. This dimension reflects if children	Children's academic skills	PISA
	Children complete compulsory education	PIAAC
	Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels	PIAAC
	Children attend higher levels of non-compulsory education	PIAAC
BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS		
Political leadership. Legal framework conditioning children's effective integration by providing access to rights and allocating resources and services.	Legislation and Practice Conditioning (LPC) acquisition of nationality	MIPEX
	LPC acquisition of permanent residence	MIPEX
	Provisions and efforts to ensure equal access to education	MIPEX
	Provisions and efforts to ensure equal access to health care	MIPEX
School segregation. Uneven distribution of migrant-background students in disadvantaged schools.	Concentration in disadvantaged schools	PISA
School organization & teachers cluster. School's organizational leadership and management	Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values, against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes	Primary data collection

towards inclusive and intercultural education.	Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally	Primary data collection
	Legislation, Recommendations, and Resources (LRR) for intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally	MIPEX
	School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities, and parental associations	Primary data collection
Learning support cluster. Availability of support in different learning domains and extra-curricular activities at the school and out-of-school contexts, and children’s attendance to these services.	LRR on preparatory classes	Eurydice
	LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support	MIPEX
	Supplementary community services for learning/language support	Primary data collection
	Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres	Primary data collection
Mental health services cluster. Availability of counselling and therapeutic services in the school or otherwise.	Counselling services at school	Primary data collection
Negative attitudes cluster. Children’s subjective perceptions and experiences on negative attitudes or mistreatment towards them.	Experience and perception of negative attitudes	Primary data collection
	Experience of harassment/physical violence outside the family	Primary data collection

3 Methodology Overview

This report focuses on the final results for all 30 indicators to map refugee and migrant children’s integration according to IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators. The report provides a synthetic analysis bringing together the information obtained from both primary data collection (which has previously been presented in D3.4 and D3.5) and secondary documentary sources. Data for 14 of the selected indicators was already available and have been collected from existing open sources such as Eurostat, MIPEX, or PISA. The technical details of these indicators are provided in Annex 1. Data for 16 of the selected indicators was obtained in IMMERSE large-scale quantitative data

collection in Belgium, Greece, Germany, Italy, Ireland and Spain. The resulting datasets encompass information from 24,419 children and 406 sites in formal and non-formal educational environments. A full report of the sample composition and data analyses for formal educational settings and other experiential environments out of the schools is presented in D3.4 and D3.5.

In addition, qualitative case-studies were conducted. These case studies focused on the lived experiences of 91 children with migrant backgrounds who are particularly marginalized and frequently under-represented in large-scale data collection, such as Unaccompanied Minors.

4 Mapping the results onto the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators

This section summarizes the results on all 30 indicators by bringing together all the collected data, including primary and secondary sources. The next section presents Integration results (14 indicators organized into five dimensions) and the following one presents Barriers and facilitators of integration (16 indicators organized into six clusters).

4.1 INTEGRATION RESULTS

The results for the indicators on integration are summarized in Table 2 by depicting the percentage of migrant-background children with positive integration results (e.g. having trust in institutions, not being an early leaver).

Table 2: Cross Country Comparisons of the Results

		Spain	Ireland	Italy	Germany	Greece	Belgium	
ACCESS TO RIGHTS	Scholarisation rates	98%	100%	95%	81%	51%	100%	1 (b)
	Unmet health care needs (no)	100%	98%	99%	100%	97%	97%	2 (c)
LANGUAGE & CULTURE	Language competence	86%	75%	76%	67%	57%	62%	2 (a)
	Intercultural ties	47%	46%	35%	58%	36%	59%	2 (a)
WELL-BEING	Happiness	82%	88%	79%	76%	84%	82%	2 (a)
	Belonging	58%	55%	38%	43%	50%	35%	2 (a)
SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS	Friends support	61%	53%	41%	60%	58%	52%	2 (a)
	Friends' diversity	49%	45%	49%	60%	40%	59%	2 (a)
	Teachers' support	68%	62%	47%	51%	59%	51%	2 (a)
	Trust in institutions	73%	75%	65%	60%	71%	60%	2 (a)
EDUCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS	Low achievers (no)	56%	79%	55%	58%	46%	57%	2 (a)
	Complete compulsory education	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	2 (f)
	Early leavers (no)	73%	na	71%	71%	79%	89%	3 (d)

	Complete upper-secondary/univ	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	forthcoming	2 (f)
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¹ % foreign; ² % migrant-background; ³ % foreign-born
 (a) 2021-23, (b) 2021-22, (c) 2021, (d) 2022, (e) 2018, (f) 2024

These results show significant cross-national variations in children’s integration results in different national contexts in Europe. The majority of IMMERSE countries perform well on access to rights for compulsory education and healthcare. This suggests that the fundamental educational and healthcare needs of migrant children are generally met across Europe.

Aside from these, the indicators where all countries have the most positive integration results are host country language competence and self-reported happiness levels of migrant children. While the findings on happiness are very positive, the finding on a related well-being dimension indicator, belonging, are less positive. Migrant children in all countries experience lower levels of belonging at school (also relative to native children). Similarly, migrant children also report relatively low levels of intercultural ties, with significant numbers not feeling close to their culture of origin, which is important to note as connections to host country and country of origin are important for positive educational (Timm, 2016) and psycho-social outcomes (Berry et al., 2006).

In relation to the dimension of social connectedness, Spain and Ireland have the most positive overall results compared to the other countries. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that all countries, including Spain and Ireland, report low levels of diversity within children's friendship groups. This lack of diversity can potentially negatively impact social connectedness. More positively, institutional trust is high in most countries for migrant children, though Germany and Belgium have slightly lower rates than the other four countries.

There are mixed findings in relation to educational achievement. Ireland has the highest level of academic achievement for migrant background children, but the results are not that positive in other countries, and particularly in Greece. In fact, all countries other than Ireland report a gap between migrant and non-migrant children’s academic achievement. Where data on early exit from education is available, Belgium performs best, with Germany and Italy reporting the lowest proportion of migrant children who remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels. There are indications from the data that countries could improve outcomes in this area and support migrant children to continue in education beyond compulsory school age. The next section discusses the findings for each dimension in more detail.

ACCESS TO RIGHTS

The first indicator in this dimension of integration is access to compulsory education. The scholarisation rates of migrant-background children varies across partner countries, with 100% enrolment of foreign-born children, or close, in Ireland and Belgium, and Spain and Italy. However, this percentage decreases to 81% in Germany and a concerning 51% in Greece⁵ (see Table 2). All EU countries, including the six IMMENSE countries, have legislation guaranteeing all children's right to formal compulsory education, irrespective of migration status. Ideally, then, all foreign children of compulsory school ages should be enrolled in compulsory school levels, but the scholarisation rates above show that this is not happening in all cases and that there are particularly challenging issues in Greece around education access for migrant background children. Additional evidence from our qualitative case studies also indicates that some unaccompanied minors in Greece had difficulties accessing compulsory education.

Regarding access to healthcare, all countries perform very well, with virtually all migrant children under 16 that reside in private households having their healthcare needs met.⁶ Greece is the country with the lowest scores in these two indicators, indicating that migrant children face greater difficulties accessing these essential social services compared to their counterparts in other countries.

LANGUAGE AND CULTURE DIMENSION

In relation to competency in host country language, the data indicates varying levels of competence in the main language of the country of residence, with Spain having the highest levels (86%) and Greece the lowest (57%) (see Table 2). According to the full data, high degrees of competence are less frequent among first-generation migrant children as compared to second generation and native children in four countries (Spain, Germany, Belgium and Greece) (see D3.4). Furthermore, competency across all partner countries was higher for second generation migrants than first generation migrants. As an indicator of integration, these results are promising, indicating effective language support measures in general as well greater intergenerational integration. Moreover, the IMMENSE qualitative case studies indicate children's interest in and keen willingness to learn host country language and, indeed, other European languages more generally. They appreciated

⁵ The IMMENSE Greek Research team identified several reasons which contribute to the lower enrolment rates of migrant children in schools in Greece. When refugee children, and their families or UAM are moving places, camps, from islands to mainland, etc, they may fail the school year due to absence (114 hours of absence in a school year means you are not qualified for successful attendance). Therefore, sudden departures due to being moved for refugee accommodation and change of address impact negatively on enrolment numbers for refugee children in Greece.

⁶ The data is extracted from EU-SILC for the year 2021. The data is representative of households living in private households only, and it covers households with children under 16.

opportunities to acquire language while decrying attitudes and practices that alienated them in schools, effectively ignoring their language needs.

The indicator on intercultural ties measures whether children aged 10-18 years feel close to people based on geographical and cultural categories, with results showing cross country variations (see Table 2). In the most traditional immigration countries (Germany and Belgium) the majority of migrant-background children (almost 60%) report a strong sense of connection to both their cultures of origin and to other social groups. This is less the case in the other countries, where more children do not feel close to people from their culture of origin (see D3.4). Significantly, across all countries, only around 10% of children report feeling close exclusively to their culture of origin. Given the Council of Europe's (2008) emphasis on interculturalism and its identified association with addressing failures of post-war multicultural segregation, that migrant children express high levels of connection to host and country of origin culture, indicates a move away from cultural segregation.

WELL-BEING DIMENSION

Overall, there were high levels of happiness reported by migrant children in all the participating countries (see table 2). Migrant children in Germany reported the lowest levels of happiness (76%) whereas Ireland had the highest percentage at 86%. Age and gender also play a role in happiness levels across all partner countries, with reported happiness decreasing across all partner countries as children grow older and migrant boys expressing higher levels of happiness than migrant girls (see D3.4). Expressing happiness as an element of wellbeing as well as mental health enables integration and engagement (WHO, 2004). It is concerning, that while our data shows levels of happiness in the 70-80%, there is variation across partner countries and on average 19% of our interviewed migrant children report being unhappy. Furthermore, in Spain and Greece, 24% and 22%, respectively, of unaccompanied minors reported not being happy (see D3.5).

There is a contrasting picture when it comes to children's sense of 'belonging' at school, a reflection of how much children feel a sense of security, identity, and community in their school in the host country, where results are much more modest across the board. Spain and Ireland have the highest levels of belonging, while Italy and Belgium have the lowest reported levels (See Table 2). While migrant-background children generally report a strong sense of belonging, statistically significant differences exist in Spain and Ireland between children from migrant backgrounds and non-migrant children (see D3.4). Furthermore, the intersection of gender, age, and migration status is a

significant factor affecting feelings of belonging, with migrant boys slightly more likely to report a higher sense of belonging than girls, and a decline in this sense of belonging as children age. These intersections underscore the importance of considering age and gender when providing support for the socio-educational integration of migrant children as the need for belonging and social acceptance is fundamental, especially for adolescent well-being (Raabe, 2019).

SOCIAL CONNECTIONS DIMENSION

There is significant country-level variation in the results pertaining to the dimensions of social connections in the data. Concerning peer support and connectedness, over half of the surveyed children with migrant backgrounds felt that they had high levels of support from their friends and peers, except in the case of Italy, where this percentage decreases to 41%. Spain reported the highest levels of belonging (61%). Differences also emerge in the data when considering first- and second-generation migrant children, with age and gender emerging as influential factors in how children perceive support from their friends and peers (see D3.4).

While in most countries approximately half of migrant participants report having many friends from diverse cultures and countries of origin, there is wide variation between countries, with Greece having a lower level of reported diversity among friends (40%) and Belgium and Germany higher (59% and 60%). It is noteworthy that in all countries, the percentage of children with many friends born in different countries or from different cultures, significantly increases among those with migrant backgrounds, while native children tend to have fewer such connections.

In relation to interconnectedness with teachers, although most migrant children reported high levels of support from their teachers, there are variations between countries. Spain has the highest level of reported support (68%), while this is the lowest in Italy (47%). Similar to other findings there are some differences in perceived support from teachers related to gender, age and first- and second-generation migrant background.

The final indicator included in this dimension is institutional trust.⁷ The findings demonstrate high levels of trust in societal institutions among children with migrant backgrounds, with healthcare institutions being the most trusted entity. There are higher levels of institutional trust in Spain, Ireland and Greece (over 70%) and Germany and Greece have the lowest levels (60%). First-generation migrant background children in a number of countries had higher levels of trust in teachers and schools than their peers indicating the important role that schools play in integration

⁷ This result averages trust levels in three institutional realms: education, healthcare and police and justice systems.

processes for migrant children. Moreover, there are variations in trust levels in teachers and schools across different countries, prompting important questions about how to bolster such trust at the national level. The police and justice system were the least trusted institutions among migrant children, with varying results at the country level, including differences in trust levels between first- and second-generation migrants. Gender and age also exerted an influence on the levels of institutional trust reported by the study participants across all areas.

EDUCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS

In relation education achievement, the first indicator is academic skills and considers the share of low achievers in reading, mathematics and science according to the 2018 PISA results. Ireland has the highest level of academic achievement for migrant background children, with only 20% low achievers.⁸ The results are not that positive in the other countries, particularly in Greece, where over 50% are low achievers. Furthermore, all countries other than Ireland report a gap between migrant and non-migrant children's academic achievement, which is the largest in Germany and Belgium (around 20 percentage points) as compared to Greece, Spain or Italy (around 10 percentage points of difference) (see Appendix 1).

The second indicator considers the proportion of early leavers according to Eurostat.⁹ Belgium performs best among migrant-background children (only around 10% early exit education), while Germany and Italy present the worst results (around 30% early leave education). There are indications from the data that countries could improve outcomes in this area and support migrant children to continue in education beyond compulsory school age. In all IMMERSE countries where data is available migrant-background students are more likely to early leave education than non-migrant students, with a gap close to 20 percentage points, except in the case of Belgium where this is reduced to 6 percentage points (see Appendix 1).

⁸ Immigrants in Ireland tend to be highly educated (Darmody and Smyth 2017) and may have higher levels of educational capital to support their own children's educational attainment than migrant groups in other IMMERSE partner countries.

⁹ "Early leaver" refers to a person aged 18 to 24 who has completed at most lower secondary education and is not involved in further education or training (Eurostat).

4.2 BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS OF SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL INTEGRATION

We summarize the barriers and facilitators results in Table 3 by depicting, depending on the type of indicator, either the percentage of schools (or migrant-background children) with positive results – such as providing adapted channels for parental participation, or not having experienced bullying – or policy scores ranging from 0 to 100 (where a higher score denotes a more positive result), as defined by MIPEX.¹⁰

Table 3: Barriers and Facilitators of Integration

		Spain	Ireland	Italy	Germany	Greece	Belgium	
POLITICAL LEADERSHIP	Policy on Citizenship	30	79	40	42	40	65	1 (c)
	Policy on Permanent residence	75	50	67	54	46	75	1 (c)
	Policy on Access to education	50	34	34	42	50	50	1 (c)
	Policy on Access to healthcare	81	85	79	63	48	73	1 (c)
SCHOOL SEGREGATION	Concentration in disadvantaged schools (no)	72%	85%	69%	61%	74%	59%	2 (d)
SCHOOL ORGANIZATION & TEACHERS	School identity around intercultural values	79%	69%	54%	57%	57%	62%	3 (a)
	Intercultural competences in syllabus	45%	40%	56%	86%	35%	50%	3 (a)
	Policy on Intercultural education	25	50	50	50	50	100	1 (c)
	School promotion of parental involvement	55%	60%	44%	14%	65%	50%	3 (a)
LEARNING SUPPORT	Policy on Preparatory classes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	4 (b)
	Policy on Educational support	50	50	33	50	50	88	1 (c)
	Supplemental language/learning	54%	31%	50%	52%	68%	45%	2 (a)
	Extra-curricular activities	59%	70%	59%	67%	61%	59%	2 (a)
MENTALHEALTH SERVICES	Counselling services at school	51%	35%	44%	38%	67%	44%	3 (a)
NEGATIVE ATTITUDES	Avoid places for fear (no)	67%	52%	58%	57%	58%	57%	2 (a)
	Bullying (no)	67%	53%	61%	57%	67%	56%	2 (a)

* All five identified topics included; ** At least 1 channel of participation adapted to parents' need (e.g. language, etc.)

¹ country score (1-100); ² % migrant-background; ³ % schools; ⁴ policy provision, recommendation or guideline

(a) 2021-23, (b) 2023, (c) 2019, (d) 2018

Cells shown in *grey cursive* have a very small n and have limited reliability.

The results indicate that there are cross-national variations in the barriers and facilitators migrant children experience in different national contexts in Europe. The results in terms of learning support demonstrate positive for all countries: on the one hand, all countries have some policy,

¹⁰ The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) identifies and measures integration policies in eight policy areas using 58 indicators which are defined against the highest European and International standards aimed at achieving equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities for all residents. Within each of the 8 policy areas, the indicator scores are averaged together to give the policy area score. For further details, see: <https://www.mipex.eu/download-pdf>

recommendations or funding for preparatory classes or language learning support, and a high proportion of migrant children attend extra-curricular activities. However, the data on political leadership highlights significant areas for improvement in all countries, underscoring the need for enhanced leadership in promoting migrant integration. Scores for citizenship policies are low in all countries except for Ireland, emphasizing the need for policy improvements in this domain. Policy on access to education, which encompasses compulsory and non-compulsory levels up to university, is another crucial area requiring improvement, with Ireland and Italy particularly struggling in this regard. Moreover, in all countries except Ireland, migrant background children are more likely to be concentrated in disadvantaged schools than their native peers.

In relation to school organisation and teachers there is wide variation in cross-country results in all of the areas indicating different patterns in how countries allocate priority and resources to this area. For instance, Greece has low overall outcomes in this area, except for school promotion of parental involvement through adapted channels. Spain scores highest in school identity in intercultural values but has low scores in intercultural education at the meso and macro levels. While Ireland performs well in school identity and parental involvement, but it has a very low score in the intercultural competency as part of the syllabuses. All countries exhibit low scores in terms of mental health services, indicating the urgent need for enhancements in this support area. At the European level, there is a clear mandate for improving mental health services to better cater to the needs of migrant children. In relation to negative attitudes the findings highlight the importance of addressing harassment and bullying as a large minority of the migrant-background children in the study report having been bullied at some point. Being subjected to bullying has been associated with reduced happiness for migrant background children, as highlighted by Correa-Velez et al. (2010). The next provides more detail and discussion of the findings for each dimension.

POLITICAL LEADERSHIP

Results on the role of political leadership as a barrier or facilitator of integration indicate that there are improvements to be made in relation to country-level policies and how these policies support socio-educational integration of migrant children (See Table 3). The first two indicators represent the legislation and practice conditioning the acquisition of superior legal status for migrants, and they are based on the MIPEX country scores for Citizenship and Permanent Residence. In the IMMERSE partner countries Belgium scores highest for these two indicators and Greece is the lowest performing country. Generally, all countries except Ireland have lower MIPEX scores on their Policy on Citizenship compared to their Policy on Residence. Spain for example while scoring

highly on the Permanent Residence indicator, has the lowest score in the Citizenship indicator. The pattern in Ireland is different as it scores the highest on their Policy on Citizenship but has one of the lowest MIPEX score on Permanent Residence. All countries need to make significant improvements on their policies regarding migrants' possibilities to acquire superior legal statuses.

The third indicator of political leadership is national legislation and practice conditioning access to education (up to higher education), and is based on the MIPEX policy score on Access to Education. All countries have relatively low scores on this indicator, and this was linked to their restrictive policies on access to higher education (see Appendix 1). Ireland and Italy have the lowest scores on this indicator. Several countries have high scores on whether compulsory and non-compulsory education is a legal right for all categories of migrants (Belgium, Greece and Spain scored 100 indicating, no restrictions in law on access for any migrant categories). However, only German scores above 0 in access to higher education, indicating that in the remaining five IMMERSE countries there is no specific targeted measures to increase migrant access to higher education or to the academic routes that lead to this type of education. This would indicate that migrant background youth face a number of significant barriers accessing higher education in all IMMERSE countries.

The fourth indicator of political leadership measures the legislation and practice conditioning access to health care, and it is based on the MIPEX indicator on Policy on Access to Health, which measures the responsiveness of national health systems to immigrant needs. Greece has the lowest level of access to healthcare for migrants according to this indicator while Spain and Ireland have the highest levels of access (See Table 3). As discussed above for integration results, Greece also has a slightly higher level of unmet need for medical examinations for migrant children, although in all countries there is very little difference between migrant and non-migrant children regarding unmet medical need (see Table 2).

SCHOOL SEGREGATION

Data indicates different country patterns in the concentration of migrant children in disadvantaged schools.¹¹ The lowest levels of concentration are found in Ireland (15%), and the highest in Germany and Belgium (40%). Moreover, in all countries except Ireland, migrant background children are more likely to be concentrated in disadvantaged schools than their native peers (see Appendix 1). The

¹¹ We define disadvantaged schools as those where over 50% of students have a low socioeconomic status (meaning they belong to the lower percentiles of the distribution within each country).

gap is particularly large in Belgium and Germany, indicating an element of school segregation for migrant children in these countries.

SCHOOL ORGANIZATION & TEACHERS

There is a notably high level of support among schools for promoting intercultural values in their educational settings, with some variations at the country level.¹² However, a significant finding across several participating IMMERSE countries was a low score for Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally (see D3.4). This data highlights potential deficiencies in leadership concerning intercultural values within schools and challenges in implementation. Greece in particular had very low scores for both of these indicators indicating a need for improvement.

Intercultural education is represented in the dashboard both at the level of schools, by asking schools whether intercultural competences are part of their syllabus and classes, and at the policy level. At the school level, the inclusion of a suite of intercultural topics and competences in the school syllabus turns out to be quite imperfect (see Table 3), although a majority of schools does include some of these topics (see D3.4). But again, teachers are even less likely to include this suit of topics in their classes, which points to significant room for improvement in this level. At the policy level, Belgium scores highest on the MIPEX indicator on Intercultural education while the other IMMERSE countries perform less well, and Spain has the lowest score, mostly due to poor results in relation to teachers' training on intercultural education (see Appendix 1).

The results related to the promotion of parental involvement indicate that most of the schools offer a high number of channels or ways for parents to become involved in their children's school (see D3.4). However, as shown in Table 3, there is a discernible trend of limited adaptation of these channels to cater to the specific needs of migrant parents, including considerations for language and cultural aspects particularly, in all countries except Germany.

LEARNING SUPPORT

The first indicator for barriers and facilitators linked to learning support considers the existence of national policies on preparatory classes or language learning support at school for newly arrived

¹² The results shown in Table 3 take into account both principals and teachers' answers.

migrants.¹³ Data from Eurydice (see Appendix 1) indicates that all IMMERSE countries have provisions for preparatory classes or additional classes in the language of schooling for newly arrived migrant students at state or national level.

The second indicator represents Policy on Educational Support, which is based on MIPEX policy scores measuring whether migrant children are entitled to have their specific needs addressed in school (see Appendix 1).¹⁴ Belgium achieves the highest score (88) on this indicator while Greece has the lowest score (33), and all remaining IMMERSE countries score 50, indicating policy deficits in this area. Ireland and Greece for example receive a low score for this indicator due to inadequate measures to address the educational situation of migrant groups.

Data on supplemental language or learning support at the meso level indicates that in most countries, around half of migrant-background children are attending language or learning support either at school or in the neighbourhood. In Ireland however, this percentage is notably lower (31%), and in Greece it is notably higher (68%). Approximately 60% migrant background children in all countries declare attending extra-curricular activities or after-school learning either at school or in the neighbourhood, with a slightly higher percentage in Ireland (70%).

MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES

The average pattern across IMMERSE countries is that the majority of schools (around 60%) do not have any staff to offer psycho-social support or personal counselling to students, indicating that additional resources are needed across all countries to support concerning counselling services at school. Greece is the only country where these services are available in large majority of schools (67%), and this is the case for over half of schools in Spain.

NEGATIVE ATTITUDES

The IMMERSE data on negative attitudes as a barrier or facilitator of integration explores children's perceptions of their treatment by others, and in particular their subjective perceptions and

¹³ Newly arrived migrants can be placed into preparatory classes (sometimes called 'reception classes' or 'transition classes'), which are separate classes or lessons in which they are provided with intensive language teaching to prepare them to integrate into mainstream classes. These classes can be full time or combined with mainstream ones. But most European countries do not separate newly arrived migrants into preparatory classes but place them directly into mainstream classrooms. Where this occurs, additional language support measures are provided (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2017).

¹⁴ These involve: (1) Educational guidance at all level (advice and guidance on system and choices at all levels). (2) Provision of continuous and ongoing education support in language(s) of instruction for migrant pupils. (3) Other targeted policies such as teaching support or financial support.

experiences of negative attitudes or mistreatment towards them. The first indicator measures whether children aged 10-18 avoid places for fear of being treated badly. While in Spain this is not the case for most migrant children (67%), in the rest of countries the percentage decreases to just over half of children, meaning that a large minority of migrant children experience this sense of fear.

The second indicator explores whether children aged 7-18 have been bullied in their countries of residence. Spain and Greece have the highest number of migrant children who do not report any experience of bullying (almost 70%). But this percentage decreases in the other countries, down to just above 50% in the case of Ireland. This means that a large minority of the migrant-background children report having been bullied at some point, with a pattern that ranges between 33% (Spain and Greece) and up to 47% (Ireland). Furthermore, we find differences per gender in bullying in all countries. In all countries the differences follow the same pattern, where migrant-background girls have been bullied more than boys, although this difference is small (with a difference range of 4-10 percentage points). Children who define their gender “in another way” report bullying experiences the most. The differences relative to girls range from very small (in Italy) to dramatically large (in Germany), with a difference in percentage points ranging from 5 to 33.

4.3 MAP OF REFUGEE AND MIGRANT’S CHILDREN INTEGRATION

In this section we aim to visualize and briefly discuss the picture that emerges from the findings discussed in the above sections, which provide the first mapping of refugee and migrant’s children integration and its barriers and facilitators in the six IMMERSE countries, and by extension in Europe. Figure 1 below brings together in a radar chart all integration results for all six countries, providing a visualization of the multiple dimensions of socio-educational integration across countries.

Figure 1 Radar Graph of Cross-Country Integration Results

As outlined in the discussion, and visible in the graph, there is convergence across the countries in relation to access to healthcare, as well as high levels happiness for migrant children. The latest is among the most positive results, as optimism has been identified as an important factor influencing psychosocial resilience and acting as a protective factor for children (Masten and Motti-Stefanidi, 2020). Also visible in the chart are the areas with more need for improvement across the board. In particular, the building of intercultural ties and levels of belonging at school, which could all be fostered by bridging the gap in levels of positive and diverse relationships among peers. The chart similarly shows the areas where integration results vary the most per national contexts, starting with a significant variation in scholarization rates, and the notable differences in the levels of language competence, with high levels visible in Italy and Spain and low levels in Greece and Germany.

Spain and Ireland are the countries with best overall results.¹⁵ Spain shows particularly strong results in teachers and friends’ support and sense of belonging, but it lacks in diversity of friends and peers. Ireland results are particularly good for academic skills, trust in institutions and happiness, but in lacks in friends’ support and diversity. Germany and Belgium excel in intercultural

¹⁵ With top scores in five and four indicators.

ties and friends’ diversity, but they run last in trust in institutions. Both countries share a common pattern in almost all integration results (see Figure 2 below). Italy results tend to be intermediate, but they significantly lack in friends’ and teacher’s support, as well as in intercultural ties. Greece is the country with the worst overall results, with four particular areas in need of improvement: scholarization rates, academic skills, intercultural ties, and friends’ diversity.

Figure 2 Radar Graph of Integration Results per countries

Figure 3 below depicts in the same way all barriers and facilitators for all six countries, thus visualising the multiple dimensions of socio-educational integration in a compact space, allowing for cross-country comparisons.

Figure 3 Radar Graph of Cross-Country Barriers and Facilitators

As outlined in the discussion, and visible in the graph, there is convergence across the countries in relation to policies to support language learning from newly arrived migrants (“preparatory classes”). And the area where most clearly there is more need for improvement across the board is access to education, including higher education levels, and the provision of counselling services at schools, where all countries except Greece falter significantly.

The chart largely shows that there is wide variation in the barriers and facilitators in different national contexts, indicating different patterns in how countries allocate priority and resources, and also different areas for improvement and replication of good practices. Spain shows again the best overall results, but it falls behind significantly in its policies on citizenship and intercultural education. Ireland, Greece and Belgium excel in several areas each, but they also have different areas for improvement. In the case of Ireland, the results fall behind particularly in terms of negative attitudes (fear and bullying experiences), supplemental learning support and counselling services. For Greece, this is particularly the case for permanent residence, access to healthcare and intercultural competences in schools’ syllabus, while in Belgium the main area for improvement is a high level of concentration in disadvantaged schools. Italy lacks in particular in access to education and educational support at the policy level, and in school identity around intercultural values. The main area for improvement in Germany is the promotion of parental involvement adapted to parents’ needs, which lacks significantly behind.

Figure 4. Radar Graph of Integration Results per countries

5 Conclusion

This report assesses how different countries facilitate the socio-educational integration of migrant children and explores the barriers and facilitators that influence their experiences. The analysis presented in this report highlights significant cross-national variations in the support systems and challenges faced by migrant children in Europe. While certain indicators of integration, such as language competence and happiness levels, exhibit promising results, challenges persist in areas such as belonging, intercultural ties, friendship diversity and educational achievement gaps. The data also highlights the intersections in migrant children’s lives and identities as difference emerge related to gender, age and migrant generation.

There are also particularly significant challenges in relation to policies on citizenship and policies on permanent residency in many of the IMMERSE countries. In addition, education policies which efforts to extend educational opportunities beyond compulsory schooling need to be reviewed in several countries to support migrant children in their educational journeys. Additionally, efforts to extend educational opportunities beyond compulsory schooling could yield significant benefits. This analysis suggests that countries have opportunities to enhance their support systems and policies to better serve the needs of migrant children, ultimately promoting their successful integration into European societies. The results and the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators are a useful tool to identify areas for intervention at national and European levels and present opportunities for cross-country comparison and learning.

6 References

- Bajo Marcos, E. Serrano, E. Fernandez Garcia, M. (2021) The antecedents of well-being in first-generation migrant children: A systematic review. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being* 13(3): 485-711.
- Berry, J.W., Phinney, J., David, S. and Vedder, P. (2016) 'Immigrant youth: Acculturation, identity and adaptation'. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 55 (3), 303 – 332.
- Bronfenbrenner, U., & Morris, P. A. (2007). The bioecological model of human development. In *Handbook of child psychology: Theoretical models of human development* (Vol. 1, pp. 793). (Handbook of child psychology). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470147658.chpsy0114>
- Correa-Velez, I., S. M. Gifford, and A. G. Barnett. 2010. "Longing to Belong: Social Inclusion and Wellbeing among Youth with Refugee Backgrounds in the First Three Years in Melbourne, Australia." *Social Science & Medicine* 71 (8): 1399–1408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2010.07.018>.
- Darmody, M., and E. Smyth. 2017. "Out-of-school Social Activities among Immigrant-Origin Children Living in Ireland." *Economic and Social Studies*. 48 (4): 419–439.
- European Agency for Fundamental Rights (2019) Integration of young refugees in the EU: good practices and challenges.
- European Commission / EACEA / Eurydice, 2022. *Structural indicators for monitoring education and training systems in Europe – 2022: Overview of major reforms since 2015*. Eurydice background report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Eurostat (2023) *Early leavers from education and training by sex and country of birth (data)*. Available in https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EDAT_LFSE_02/default/table
- Eurydice (2017 and 2023) Key data on teaching languages at school in Europe – 2023 edition, available at: [Key data on teaching languages at school in Europe – 2023 edition \(eurydice.eu\)](https://eurydice.eu/key-data-on-teaching-languages-at-school-in-europe-2023-edition/)
- Koehler, C., Schneider, J. Young refugees in education: the particular challenges of school systems in Europe. *CMS* 7, 28 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-019-0129-3>
- Lundy, L and McEvoy, L. (2012) Children's rights and research processes: Assisting children to (in)formed views. *Childhood*. Volume 19, Issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.1177/090756821140907>
- OECD (2022) *PIAAC Data and Tools*, available here <https://www.oecd.org/skills/piaac/data/>
- Masten, A. and Motti-Stefanidi,, F. (2020) 'Multisystem Resilience for Children and Youth in Disaster: Reflections in the Context of COVID-19' *Advers Resil Sci*.1(2): 95 106. doi: [10.1007/s42844-020-00010-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s42844-020-00010-w)
- PISA (2018) PISA 2018 Database: <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/data/2018database/>

Raabe, I. J. 2019. "Social Exclusion and School Achievement: Children of Immigrants and Children of Natives in Three European Countries." *Child Indicators Research* **12** (3): 1003–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12187-018-9565-0>.

Timm, M. 2016. "The Integration of Refugees into the German Education System: A Stance for Cultural Pluralism and Multicultural Education." *E-Journal of Education Policy* 16: 1–7.

7 Appendix

Appendix 1: Overview of IMMERSE secondary-source based indicators

FOR INTEGRATION RESULTS

Children's access to compulsory education (Access to rights dimension)

Scholarization rates, proxied by: foreign children enrolled at school as a share of foreign children in compulsory ages¹⁶

	% foreign children enrolled at school Relative to foreign children in compulsory school ages			
	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
Belgium	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
Germany	83	83	83	81
Ireland	100	100	100	100
Greece	36	30	27	51
Spain	100	100	97	98
Italy	97	94	92	95

Data source (1): Eurostat (for population figures). Available in https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/MIGR_POP2CTZ_custom_7455372/default/table

Data source (2): National ministries of education or statistics services (students in compulsory education)

*Note: The indicator refers to **registered**, rather than attending children. We use **citizenship** as a proxy of migrant-background (which refers to country of birth and parents' country of birth) because data on school enrolment is usually only available by citizenship and not by migration-background.*

Children's access to health care (access to rights dimension)

Difference in the share of children under 16 that had unmet needs for medical examination in the last 12 months among migrant-background and native respondents.

¹⁶ Ideally, the rate should be 100, meaning that all foreign children in compulsory school ages in the country are enrolled in compulsory school levels.

(* An upper bound has been established at 100 for rates over 100 (i.e. foreign population enrolled in compulsory levels is shown to be larger than the reference population as registered in Eurostat). This is theoretically possible because: (1) there could be older children in these grades (repetition), and in some cases younger ones (starting primary at earlier age); (2) there is a several-months mismatch in the registration dates (population in January, school students by the end of the summer); (3) the population registers might not cover all population (e.g. irregular or transit situation), underestimating the actual population that could end up enrolled in schools)

	2021		
	%		Difference
	Migrant-background	Native children	
Belgium	3.99%	1.15%	-2.84%
Germany	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Ireland	9.74%	8.12%	-1.62%
Greece	4.51%	1.04%	-3.48%
Spain	4.68%	4.23%	-0.45%
Italy	3.31%	2.33%	-0.98%

Data source: EU-SILC, available here <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/european-union-statistics-on-income-and-living-conditions>

Note: this indicator is based on the same question included in the EU indicators for migrant integration (Zaragoza Indicators), only referred to children under 16. This question (available in 2017 special module and 2021 wave) is answered by adult respondents in households with children under 16. The data is thus representative of households with children under 16, rather than representative of this population as such

Children's academic skills (Educational achievements dimension)

Difference in the share of low achievers in reading, mathematics and science among migrant-background and native children (15-year-olds)¹⁷

	2018		
	%		Difference
	Migrant-background	Native children	
Belgium	42,6	21,7	20,9
Germany	41,6	22,6	19,0
Ireland	21,3	24,5	-3,2
Greece	53,9	43,9	10,0
Spain	44,1	33,1	11,0
Italy	44,9	34,0	10,9

Data source: PISA, available here: <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/data/2018database/>

Note: low achievers are those students who score below Level 2 (considered the baseline level of proficiency that is required to participate fully in society) on the PISA mathematics, reading and/or science scales. For a more detailed description see the PISA 2012 Technical Report (OECD, 2014). The data only covers 15-year-old children.

¹⁷ Ideally, the difference should be 0 (no difference between migrant-background and native persons). A positive difference means migrant-background children in the country are more affected by low achievement in basic academic skills.

Children complete compulsory education (Educational achievements dimension)

Difference in the share of persons aged 16-20 with compulsory education completed among migrant-background persons (if arrived in the host country before age 15) and natives¹⁸

	2024
Belgium	Forthcoming*
Germany	Forthcoming*
Ireland	Forthcoming*
Greece *	Forthcoming*
Spain	Forthcoming*
Italy *	Forthcoming*

Data source: PIAAC, available here <https://www.oecd.org/skills/piaac/data/>

Note: Data for this indicator will be in 2024: data collection for the PIAAC 2nd Cycle of the Survey of Adult Skills (PIAAC) is taking place from 2022-2023 and the results will be published (and incorporated) in 2024. Although data is available for the year 2012, this has been deemed to be too distant in time to be informative of the current situation.

Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels (Educational achievements dimension)

Difference in share of early leavers among foreign-born and non-foreign born (aged 18-24)¹⁹

	2022		Difference
	%		
	Migrant-background	Native children	
Belgium	11,4	5,6	5,8
Germany	28,8	9,4	19,4
Ireland	na	3,6	na
Greece	20,9	3,7	17,2
Spain	27,1	11,2	15,9
Italy	28,7	9,7	19

Data source: Eurostat. Available in https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EDAT_LFSE_02/default/table

Note: “early leavers” refers to a person aged 18 to 24 who has completed at most lower secondary education and is not involved in further education or training (Eurostat). Early school leaving is one of the most studied and cited indicator of the last decade, and it is widely used in several indicators system and policy monitoring plans (European Education Area Targets, Youth Dashboard of the EU youth strategy, EU indicators for migrant integration (Zaragoza Indicators) and others). It asks about an age group already entering adult life (18-24), but

¹⁸ Ideally, the difference should be 0 (no difference between migrant-background and native persons). A negative difference means migrant-background children in the country do not complete compulsory education in larger proportions than natives.

¹⁹ Ideally, the difference should be 0 (no difference between foreign-born and non-foreign born). A positive difference means foreign-born persons in the country are more affected by school early-leaving than natives.

since we are interested on whether children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels, we need to consider an age range beyond the compulsory age, which is 18 in Belgium and Germany (16 in Spain, Ireland, Italy, and 15 in Greece).

Types & levels of formal non-compulsory education attended (Educational achievements dimension)

Difference in share of persons aged 16-24 who have completed (or who are currently studying) upper secondary or tertiary studies in the survey country among migrant-background and native population²⁰

	2024		
	%		Difference
	Migrant-background	Native children	
Belgium	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*
Germany	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*
Ireland	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*
Greece *	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*
Spain	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*
Italy *	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*	Forthcoming*

Data source: PIAAC, available here <https://www.oecd.org/skills/piaac/data/>

Note: Data for this indicator will be in 2024: data collection for the PIAAC 2nd Cycle of the Survey of Adult Skills (PIAAC) is taking place from 2022-2023 and the results will be published (and incorporated) in 2024. Although data is available for the year 2012, this has been deemed to be too distant in time to be informative of the current situation.

FOR BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS

Legislation and practice conditioning the acquisition of superior legal status (Political leadership cluster)

- (1) MIPEX²¹ policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Citizenship
- (2) MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Permanent Residence

	2019	
	Citizenship	Permanent Residence
Belgium	65	75
Germany	42	54
Ireland	79	50
Greece	40	46

²⁰ Ideally, the difference should be 0 (no difference between migrant-background and native population). A negative difference means migrant-background persons in the country do not complete upper secondary or tertiary education in larger proportions than natives.

²¹ The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) identifies and measures integration policies in eight policy areas using 58 indicators which are defined against the highest European and International standards aimed at achieving equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities for all residents. Within each of the 8 policy areas, the indicator scores are averaged together to give the policy area score.

Spain	30	75
Italy	40	67

Data source: MIPEX, available: <https://www.mipex.eu/download-pdf>

Note: The Citizenship score measures whether legal immigrants are encouraged to naturalise and whether their children born in the country are entitled to become full citizens. It does so by averaging the scores in 8 different indicators. The Permanent Residence score measures whether legal immigrants are encouraged to naturalise and whether temporary legal residents have facilitated access to a long-term residence permit. It does so by averaging the scores in 7 different indicators. For further details, see MIPEX explanation of Policy Indicators Scores (2007-2019) available [here](#).

Legislation and practice conditioning access to education (Political leadership cluster)

MIPEX policy score (0-100) for Access to Education (Education Strand)

	2019		
	Access to compulsory and non-compulsory education	Access to higher education	Average
Belgium	100	0	50
Germany	33	50	42
Ireland	67	0	34
Greece	100	0	50
Spain	100	0	50
Italy	67	0	34

Data source: MIPEX, available: <https://www.mipex.eu/download-pdf>

Note: this indicator averages the score in the two MIPEX indicators on access to education, which are: (1) Access to compulsory and non-compulsory education (e.g. pre-primary, vocational training, university education), which measures whether access to both compulsory and non-compulsory education is a legal right for all categories of migrants in the country. (2) Access to higher education, which measures support to access university education. The indicator considers both measures to increase migrant pupils' access to academic routes that lead to higher education and to increase acceptance and successful participation. For further details, see MIPEX explanation of Policy Indicators Scores (2007-2019) available [here](#).

Legislation and practice conditioning access to health care (Political leadership cluster)

MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Health

	2019
	Health
Belgium	73
Germany	63
Ireland	85
Greece	48
Spain	81
Italy	79

Data source: MIPEX, available: <https://www.mipex.eu/download-pdf>

Note: this score measures the health system is responsive to immigrants' needs. It does so by averaging the scores in 12 different indicators, considering aspects such as conditions for inclusion in the system of health care coverage, administrative discretion and documentation requirements, or provision of information and interpreters. For further details, see MIPEX explanation of Policy Indicators Scores (2007-2019) available [here](#).

Concentration of migrant-background children in disadvantaged schools (School segregation cluster)

Difference in the share of students enrolled in disadvantaged schools among migrant-background and native students²²

	2018		
	%		Difference
	Migrant-background	Native children	
Belgium	40,8	17,7	23,1
Germany	39,1	22,3	16,8
Ireland	14,9	15	-0,1
Greece	26,4	17,3	9,1
Spain	27,7	18	9,7
Italy	31,4	21,5	9,9

Data source: PISA, available here: <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/data/2018database/>

Note: Disadvantaged schools are those with over 50% of students with low socioeconomic status (this is defined as being in the lower percentiles within each country). The data only covers 15-year olds (PISA design), and thus excludes primary-level schools.

Legislation, Resources and Recommendations on Intercultural education (School organization and teachers cluster)

MIPEX policy score (0-100) for "Intercultural Education For All" (Education Strand)

	2019		
	School curriculum to reflect diversity	Teacher training to reflect diversity	Average
Belgium	100	100	100
Germany	50	50	50
Ireland	50	50	50
Greece	50	50	50
Spain	50	0	25
Italy	50	50	50

Data source: MIPEX, available: <https://www.mipex.eu/download-pdf>

Note: This indicator averages the score in two MIPEX indicators aiming to measure whether all pupils and teachers are supported to learn and work together in a diverse society, which are: (1) School curriculum, which

²² Ideally, there should be no concentration of disadvantaged students at schools, so the number of these “disadvantaged schools” (and the percentage of students enrolled in them) should be close to 0. A positive difference in this indicator means that migrant-background children in the country are more affected by this concentration problem than native children.

measures whether appreciation of cultural diversity is included either as stand-alone curriculum subject or integrated throughout the curriculum. (2) Teacher training, which measures whether teachers' training and professional development programmes require intercultural education and the appreciation of cultural diversity. For further details, see MIPEX explanation of Policy Indicators Scores (2007-2019) available [here](#).

Legislation, Resources and Recommendations on Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support (Learning support cluster)

MIPEX policy score (0-100) for "Targeting needs" (Education Strand)

	2019			Average
	Educational guidance at all level	Language instruction	Measures to address educational situation of migrant groups	
Belgium	75	100	75	88
Germany	50	50	50	50
Ireland	50	50	0	50
Greece	0	67	0	33
Spain	50	50	50	50
Italy	50	50	50	50

Data source: MIPEX, available: <https://www.mipex.eu/download-pdf>

Note: This indicator averages the score in the three MIPEX indicators aiming to measure whether migrant children are entitled to have their specific needs addressed in school, which are: (1) Educational guidance at all level, which measures access to advice and guidance on system and choices at all levels. (2) Language instruction, which measures provision of continuous and ongoing education support in language(s) of instruction for migrant pupils. (3) Measures to address situation of migrant groups, which measures other targeted policies such as teaching support or financial support. For further details, see MIPEX explanation of Policy Indicators Scores (2007-2019) available [here](#).

Legislation, Resources and Recommendations on Preparatory classes for newly arrived migrants (Learning support cluster)

Whether there are provisions of preparatory classes or additional classes in the language of schooling for newly arrived migrant students at state or national level

	2017	2023
Belgium	Yes	Yes*
Germany	Yes*	Yes*
Ireland	Yes	Yes
Greece	Yes*	Yes*
Spain	Yes	Yes*
Italy	Yes*	Yes*

Data source: Eurydice ([2017](#), [2023](#))

* The preparatory/additional classes may happen either during or outside school hours. Otherwise, they happen during school hours.

Note: Newly arrived migrants can be placed into preparatory classes (sometimes called 'reception classes' or 'transition classes'), which are separate classes or lessons in which they are provided with intensive language teaching to prepare them to integrate into mainstream classes. These classes can be full time or combined with mainstream ones. But most European countries do not separate newly arrived migrants into preparatory classes, but place them directly into mainstream classrooms. Where this occurs, additional language support measures are provided (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2017). The data reflects only measures recommended/required by central education authorities or measures financially supported by central education authorities. In many countries, there is school autonomy or regional variations in the implementation of these.